

First Case of Postpartum Acquired Hemophilia a described in Madagascar

Rajo Païdia Radinasoa^{1*}, Norosoa Eliane Sonjandrimalala¹, Julien Rakotoson², Ny Aina Nivolalanirina Andriamangarivo³, Harilala Mahefa Randrianarivony¹, Hanta Marie Danielle Vololontiana¹

¹Departement of Internal Medecine, University Hospital of Antananarivo, Antananarivo, Madagascar

²Departement of Rheumatology, University Hospital of Antananarivo, Antananarivo, Madagascar

³Departement of Clinical Hematology, University Hospital of Antananarivo, Antananarivo, Madagascar

Citation: Rajo Païdia Radinasoa, Norosoa Eliane Sonjandrimalala, Julien Rakotoson, Ny Aina Nivolalanirina Andriamangarivo, Harilala Mahefa Randrianarivony, Hanta Marie Danielle Vololontiana. *First Case of Postpartum Acquired Hemophilia a described in Madagascar. Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(14):1-6.

Received Date: 14 August, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 17 August, 2023; **Published Date:** 21 August, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Rajo Païdia Radinasoa, Departement of Internal Medecine, University Hospital of Antananarivo, Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Copyright: © Rajo Païdia Radinasoa, Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Acquired hemophilia A (AHA) is a disorder of hemostasis resulting from the development of antibodies to coagulation factor VIII (FVIII). The disease may be related to malignant pathology, autoimmune disease, drugs, the peripartum period or idiopathic. Postpartum AHA accounts for 14% of all AHA. It is caused by the development of anti-FVIII during pregnancy. It is an often serious bleeding cause, which can lead to the mother's death after delivery. Treatment is based on achieving hemostasis to stop bleeding and eliminate anti-FVIII antibodies with immunosuppressive drugs. We report the first case of postpartum AHA described in Madagascar, which was revealed by post-dental extraction persistent gingival bleeding in a 35-year-old woman at 10 months postpartum.

Keywords: Acquired hemophilia; Anti-factor VIII; Autoantibodies; Postpartum

INTRODUCTION

Acquired hemophilia A (AHA) is a disorder of hemostasis, causing bleeding syndromes that can be life-threatening in emergency. It constitutes a diagnostic and therapeutic emergency. The disease occurs in subjects with no previous history of bleeding or other hematological pathology^[1,2]. Its pathophysiology results from the occurrence of antibodies or inhibitors directed against coagulation factors VIII^[3]. It may be associated with an underlying condition such as autoimmune disease, pregnancy (postpartum), haematological malignancy or drugs^[2]. Postpartum AHA is a rare cause of AHA. The disease generally occurs after the first pregnancy, and the average age is 26^[4]. A

bleeding syndrome frequently occurs within 1 to 4 months after delivery. Bleeding occurs predominantly in the genital tract, followed by bruising or hematoma of the muscles, and rarely in the oral mucosa^[2]. Treatment is aimed at two objectives: firstly, to stop the bleeding, and secondly, to eliminate the FVIII inhibitors using immunosuppressants^[5,6]. The cause of the development of FVIII antibodies is still unclear. Our objectives are to report the first case of postpartum AHA described in our country, with its particularities, and to review the disease.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 35-year-old woman was hospitalized with gingival bleeding that had been persistent for 2 weeks before admission. The bleeding was caused by a tooth extraction and had previously benefited from surgical and electrical haemostasis, but the bleeding persisted. The patient had spontaneous ecchymosis of the lower limbs 2 months before the extraction. She has no history of known autoimmune disease, drug use or cancer. She has no hemophilic family or childhood hemorrhagic events. She had 3 pregnancies and 3 childbirths, the last 10 months ago prior to tooth extraction. On physical examination, she presented with a worsening general condition and a poorly tolerated anaemic syndrome: mucocutaneous pallor, tachycardia, hypotension and polypnoea. Bleeding was still active on admission. There was a large blood clot in the extracted tooth (Figure 1), which was replaced by another after removal. Other examinations were unremarkable. Biological tests (Table 1) showed anemia at 5 g/dl, microcytic and hypochromic (VGM 66 fl, CCHM 317); moderate hyperleukocytosis at 11.3 G/L and thrombocytosis at 498 G/L. C-reactive protein was 4 mg/l and sedimentation rate 10 mm. Hemostasis revealed an activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) 68.1 seconds longer than the control 26.2 seconds (patient aPTT/aPTT control ratio 2.6), a normal prothrombin level (PT) of 100%, and a normal fibrinogen level of 4.5 g/L. Factor VIII was low at 12.5%. Other vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors (II, VII, IX and X) and VWF (von Willebrand factor) were normal. Anti-FVIII antibody test was positive at 1.9 Bethesda Units/ml. Anti-nuclear factor and anti-DNA were negative. Based on the clinical-biological situation, we retained the diagnosis of postpartum AHA. As treatment, the patient received several bags of packed red blood cells with antihaemorrhagic agents, but the bleeding did not stop. Background corticosteroid therapy was started at 1mg/kg/d with adjuvant measures. Bleeding stopped on the second day of corticosteroid therapy (Figure 2). The patient went into complete remission 6 weeks later.

DISCUSSION

AHA is a haemostasis disorder characterized by the presence of antibodies that inhibit coagulation factor VIII. Its annual incidence is estimated at 0.2-1 cases per million inhabitants^[4]. It is generally correlated with the presence of autoimmune diseases, tumors, lympho or myeloproliferative syndromes, pregnancy, drugs or in some cases idiopathic disorders. Mortality rate is 10-20%, mainly due to severe or uncontrolled haemorrhagic events^[3,4]. The age of occurrence concerns two peaks: in the over-65 years, it mainly affects males with underlying tumor pathologies; in younger subjects aged 20 to 40, females are more affected, especially those in postpartum^[7,8]. Postpartum AHA accounts for 14% of all acquired hemophilia. It shows up early as bleeding from the genital tract, sometimes severe after delivery, especially 1 to 4 months after delivery, but later (6 months to 1 year) as

hematomas, ecchymosis, hemarthrosis or bleeding from the mucous areas. Our case presented with gingival bleeding, which according to Natacha Dewarrat et al.^[8] is reported in only 4% of postpartum AHA. The mechanism of FVIII antibody development during pregnancy is still unclear, but one hypothesis is based on the possibility of maternal exposure to fetal FVIII via transplacental passage during delivery^[3,9]. Postpartum AHA usually occurs after the first pregnancy, but rare cases are reported as late as 30% up to the 7th pregnancy^[4]. Our case joins those occurring late after the 1st pregnancy, and she had no suspected hemorrhagic events before the 3rd pregnancy. Postpartum haemorrhage is frequently diagnosed on average 60 days after delivery, with extremes from 0 to 308 days, but can be detected in the antepartum period (second trimester) by a high anti-FVIII titre, and can also be detected late, up to a year after delivery^[8,10]. Our case presented with spontaneous ecchymoses on the thighs 9 months after delivery and the onset of gingival bleeding at 10 months. The diagnosis of postpartum acquired hemophilia is evoked by a bleeding syndrome in a postpartum woman with no history of previous bleeding disorders. Haemostasis tests showed an isolated prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) with a decrease rate of FVIII. Immunological tests show a high FVIII antibodies titre exceeding 0,4 Bethesda Units^[6, 11, 12]. In practice, all postpartum women presenting a hemorrhagic syndrome with an isolated prolonged aPTT are considered to have postpartum AHA. The diagnosis is confirmed by a lower FVIII level and a high anti-FVIII titre. However, the presence of lupus anticoagulant should be ruled out in view of the clinico-biological picture, as this is the most frequent differential diagnosis of postpartum AHA. Treatment has two aims: one is to control the bleeding episode and the second is to eliminate FVIII antibodies. For the treatment of hemorrhagic events, many authors recommend the use of bypassing agents to ensure hemostasis and stop bleeding. The most widely used are FEIBA agents (factor VIII inhibitor bypassing activity) or recombinant factor VIIa as first choice. Desmopressin is used as a second-line treatment for minor bleeding episodes^[13]. For eradication or elimination of FVIII antibodies: there is no consensus, but the immunosuppressant used as first-line treatment is corticotherapy at a dose of prednisone 1mg/kg/day^[3,14]. Cyclophosphamides are also useful in severe cases, but the benefits and risks for patients must be weighed up, and management requires multidisciplinary consensus^[8]. In our case, eradication therapy was effective, stopping the bleeding on day 2, despite the unavailability of emergency bypass agents in our country. Early initiation of anti-FVIII eradication therapy would therefore be preferred in the absence of means to control bleeding. Complications of hemorrhage, on the other hand, need to be managed early, such as transfusion in the case of severe anemia such as in our case. According to the literature, FVIII antibodies may disappear spontaneously even without treatment in some cases, but may persist for several months or even a year after delivery, making it advisable to initiate immunosuppressive therapy for complete remission^[7,12]. AHA has a low mortality rate, and is currently considered a benign condition due to the good control of bleeding episodes. After treatment, postpartum AHA has a favorable evolution with complete remission in an average of 6 weeks^[8]. Relapse after complete remission during a next pregnancy is still not well known.

CONCLUSION

Postpartum AHA is a potentially life-threatening cause of bleeding syndrome in postpartum women. The diagnosis should be made early in the presence of an isolated prolonged a PTT in postpartum women, associated with a

reduced factor VIII and high anti-FVIII level. Immunosuppressive treatment (corticosteroid therapy) should be started as soon as the diagnosis is confirmed, especially in areas with limited emergency resources.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

We do not have any conflict of interest.

CONSENT STATEMENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient to publish this report in accordance with the journal's consent policy.

REFERENCES

1. Franchini M, Vaglio S, Marano G, Mengoli C, Gentili S, Pupella S, et al. Acquired hemophilia A: a review of recent data and new therapeutic options. *Hematology*, 2017; 22 (9): 514-520.
2. Knoebl P, Marco P, Baudo F, Collins P, Huth-Kühne A, Nemes L, et al. Demographic and clinical data in acquired hemophilia A: results from the European Acquired Haemophilia Registry (EACH2). *J Thromb Haemost JTH*, avr 2012; 10 (4): 622-631.
3. Poston JN, Kruse-Jarres R. Advances in Acquired Hemophilia A. *Transfus Med Rev*, 2022; 36 (4): 215-219.
4. Santoro RC, Prejanò S. Postpartum-acquired haemophilia A: a description of three cases and literature review. *Blood Coagul Fibrinolysis*, 2009; 20 (6): 461-465.
5. Seethala S, Gaur S, Enderton E, Corral J. Postpartum Acquired Hemophilia: A Rare Cause of Postpartum Hemorrhage. *Case Rep Hematol*, 2013; 2013: 1-2.
6. Dolan G, Benson G, Bowyer A, Eichler H, Hermans C, Jiménez-Yuste V, et al. Principles of care for acquired hemophilia. *Eur J Haematol*, 2021; 106 (6): 762-773.
7. Azam K, Batool Z, Malik A, Chaudhry M, Abdullah M. Postpartum-Acquired Hemophilia A Presenting as Hemoperitoneum: A Case Report. *Cureus [Internet]*, 2020.
8. Dewarrat N, Gavillet M, Angelillo-Scherrer A, Naveiras O, Grandoni F, Tsakiris DA, et al. Acquired haemophilia A in the postpartum and risk of relapse in subsequent pregnancies: A systematic literature review. *Haemophilia*, 2021; 27 (2): 199-210.
9. Lapalud P, Ali T, Cayzac C, Mathieu-Dupas E, Levesque H, Pfeiffer C, et al. The IgG autoimmune response in postpartum acquired hemophilia A targets mainly the A1a1 domain of FVIII. *J Thromb Haemost*, 2012; 10 (9): 1814-1822.
10. Kose M, Bakkaloglu OK, Amikishiyev S, Akpınar TS, Saracoglu B, Akcan T, et al. Acquired FVIII and FIX Inhibitors after Pregnancy: A Case Report. *Acta Haematol*, 2016; 136 (4): 229-232.
11. García-Chávez J, Majluf-Cruz A. Hemofilia adquirida. *Gac Médica México*, 2019; 156 (1): 3158.
12. Shobeiri SA, West EC, Md MJK, Nolan TE. Postpartum Acquired Hemophilia (Factor VIII Inhibitors): A Case Report and Review of the Literature. *Obstet Gynecol Surv*, 2000; 55 (12): 729-737.

13. Kruse-Jarres R, Kempton CL, Baudo F, Collins PW, Knoebl P, Leissing CA, et al. Acquired hemophilia A: Updated review of evidence and treatment guidance. Am J Hematol, 2017; 92 (7): 695-705.
14. Windyga J, Baran B, Odnoczek E, Buczman A, Drews K, Laudanski P, et al. Treatment guidelines for acquired hemophilia A. Ginekol Pol, 2019; 90 (6): 353-364.

Table 1: Patient's biological parameters.

Parameters	Results	References
Hemoglobin	55 g/l	120-180 g/l
VGM	66 fl	80-95 fl
CCMH	317	320-360
Leukocyte	11,3 G/L	4-10 G/L
Platelet	498 G/L	150-450 G/L
CRP	4 mg/l	< 6 mg/l
Sedimentation rate	10 mm (1st hour)	<20 mm (1st hour)
PT	100%	70-100%
QT	12,4s	13,5s
aTT	68,1s	26,2s
aTT patient/ aTT control	2.6	0.80-1.20
Factor VIII	12,5%	70-150%
Factor IX	100%	70-150%
Factor II	100%	70-120%
Factor VII	100%	70-120%
Factor X	100%	70-120%
Von Willebrand factor	150%	50-150%
Fibrinogen	4,5 g/l	2-4 g/l
Anti-factor VIII antibodies	1,9 UB/ml	<0,4 UB/ml

Figure 1: Large clot looking at tooth number 16.

Figure 2: Intact gingival lining without bleeding.